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СОВЕРШИЛ ВСЕ ВОЗМОЖНЫЕ ОШИБКИ
В ОЧЕНЬ УЗКОЙ СПЕЦИАЛЬНОСТИ.*

Нильс Бор

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TO THE PROBLEM OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE RELATED APPROACHES

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ANNOTATION. This article discusses the importance of artificial intelligence today and its impact on humanity. The stages of development of artificial intelligence and approaches to it are analyzed.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, approach, human, electronic database, internet

Nowadays, artificial intelligence has taken its place in every aspect of our lives. It helps us analyze data, automate tasks, present information, in medicine, transportation, improve the quality of services, and in many other areas. Artificial intelligence plays an important role in making tasks easier for people and making our lives simpler and more convenient. Developments in the field of artificial intelligence are leading humanity to new levels of productivity. Artificial intelligence is taking over all areas. It is becoming one of the main tools for automatic data acquisition, analysis, and automation of activities. Along with such innovations and new opportunities, security issues are becoming increasingly important. «Problems are arising related to the security of personal data, the influence of algorithms on other factors. This is due to the need to reflect, develop legal regulations and develop artificial intelligence effectively, in accordance with ethical rules. The strengthening of the role of artificial intelligence in our lives in our society deepens the problems of developing technologies in accordance with legal, ethical and security principles. This process opens up new opportunities for us, but on the other hand, it also puts us at risk due to the problems of compliance with legal and ethical norms and their preservation [1]. » Although artificial intelligence is intended to ensure the security of personal data, this goal is somewhat lagging behind in today's globalized era. Because the fundamental nature of artificial intelligence has changed.

emergence of artificial intelligence is a new stage in human civilization. Because in the era of globalization, when the need for artificial intelligence arose, its creation has provided humanity with great opportunities. Artificial intelligence has entered human life with such great intensity that today no person can imagine his life without artificial intelligence. Through it, the authorities are also looking for ways to work with the people. It is no exaggeration to say that artificial intelligence has become an assistant to humans in all areas, from medicine to education. Different definitions have been given to artificial intelligence by all countries. At this point, the question arises, what is the essence of artificial intelligence and how did it become a problem?

1980–1990s, computational scientists Barr and Feigenbaum proposed the following definition of artificial intelligence (AI):

«Artificial intelligence is the field of computer science that deals with the development of intelligent computer systems, that is, systems that have capabilities that we traditionally associate with human intelligence, including the ability to understand language, learn, reason, solve problems, and solve other problems [2].»

Artificial intelligence is an artificial mind created as a specific assistant to humans. An additional consciousness helps a person to make their work easier.

Artificial intelligence is a technology community that uses computer systems and programs to simulate human mental activity, concepts, data, and other mental tasks. Artificial intelligence helps computers perform tasks such as self-learning, analyzing concepts and data, finding logical solutions, giving advice, writing, understanding images or listening to information. Artificial intelligence began and developed with the concept of the Turing test. «The founder of the Turing test was Alan Turing In the 1950s, he discussed artificial intelligence systems in his article «Computing Machinery and Intelligence.» He proposed the Turing test, which would explain the average human's ability to think and communicate like a computer system [3]. There are several claims about what was the first artificial intelligence project in use. However, it was not until the Dartmouth Conference in 1956 that the field of artificial intelligence was formally introduced [4]. At this conference, it was stated that projects are used to serve the purpose of studying the field of artificial intelligence and stimulating its development. «The first practical artificial intelligence project is the experience of the IBM 701 computer created by IBM in 1956 and its use in other activities. This computer was mainly used for calculations and statistical processes, but it did not have the ability to pass the Turing test or think like a human. Later, developments and projects in the field of artificial intelligence were carried out through systems and algorithms used in various fields. The IBM Deep Blue computer defeated world chess

champion Garry Kasparov in 1997 with a score of 3:5 2:5 as an example of the extremely important development of artificial intelligence [5]. ” In addition, there are developing artificial intelligence projects in the expansion of industries, automation of systems in the workplace, analysis and learning in various fields, management of transportation systems, distance learning systems in education, enterprise employee evaluation systems (KPIs), and many other areas.

Types of artificial intelligence:

«**General artificial intelligence (strong).** General artificial intelligence is a level of artificial intelligence that has the ability to solve any cognitive task, perform any intellectual function, and adapt to new situations similar to human intelligence. Its characteristics include self-awareness, self-learning, adaptability, and the ability to learn various tasks similar to human intelligence. For example, general artificial intelligence does not currently exist; it is a subject of research and theoretical thinking. This artificial intelligence is an artificial intelligence that can enter any system and, having analyzed it, give advice like a human. Such artificial intelligence, despite being based on algorithms, is very complex.

Weak (narrow) artificial intelligence. Weak artificial intelligence specializes in performing specific tasks or solving a limited set of problems. It does not have the ability to learn or adapt to new situations outside its intended domain. Its characteristics include high performance in solving specific problems, but limited ability to learn and adapt. For example, search engines, recommendation systems, automatic speech recognition, computer vision, chess games.

Super AI. Super AI refers to a level of artificial intelligence that surpasses human intelligence in all aspects and tasks, including intelligence, creativity, and problem-solving. Its characteristics include the hypothetical ability to solve complex problems and create new technologies, adaptability, and self-learning beyond human capabilities. There are no concrete examples of super AI in real life yet [6]. Such super AI manifests itself through a specific technology without human command and may even have the ability to subjugate a person if necessary.

Each of these levels of artificial intelligence has its own advantages, limitations, and potential risks. Artificial intelligence has always been a concern for scientists, and various forums, agreements, debates, and meetings are held on this issue.

The debate about artificial intelligence has been going on for almost 50 years. Experts are still divided. Some are concerned that their popularity will lead to mass unemployment as they replace humans. Another group of experts advocate a positive attitude towards AI. Even among IT billionaires, there are different views.

The most dangerous aspect of the modern world based on artificial intelligence is that it is based on the principle of «winner takes all.» This is a factor that further intensifies social tensions and international conflicts.

The issue of artificial intelligence was also one of the hot topics at the **World Economic Forum**, held on January 19, 2024. The Davos 2024 conference discussed the topic [7] «**Artificial Intelligence and Emerging Technologies: 5 Surprising Things You Need to Know.**» This forum is dedicated to the issue of whether or not to regulate artificial intelligence around the world, and such forums are attended by AI creators and a number of scientists. “ According to data from early January 2024, researchers at the International Monetary Fund found that AI could affect the work of four in 10 workers worldwide. This number rises to six in 10 in developed economies in sectors as diverse as telemarketing and law. In addition, according to a report published by the World Economic Forum, half of economists said AI would be [8] a “ commercial disruptor ” in 2024, up from 42% in 2023.

«**This is the most powerful technology of our time,**» Arati Prabhakar, director of the White House Office of Science and Technology Policy, said at a panel in Davos on January 17. “ **We see the power of AI as something that needs to be managed. The risks need to be managed.**» That is, Prabhakar warned that the power of AI must be controlled, and that if it is not controlled, it will certainly bring great dangers to humanity. Many scientists argue that AI needs to be brought under control.

Andrew Ng, founder of AI education company Deep Learning AI and adjunct professor of computer science at Stanford University, told the World Economic Forum that “ regulations that impose onerous requirements on open source software or the development of AI technology can stifle innovation, have an anti – competitive effect that supports big technology, and slow down our ability to generate profits. ” That is, it is [9] assumed that limiting artificial intelligence will have a negative impact on the economy and sustainable development. Because artificial intelligence is used in almost half of the sectors of today’s societies.

say it’s not even right to try to directly govern AI technology in the first place. Rather than governing it, they say, it’s better to learn how to use it and how to use it. They argue that regulation should be targeted. That is, to the effects.

«**There are all sorts of unwritten laws around the world for AI, but they are absolutely relevant to AI. Privacy laws, cybersecurity regulations, digital safety, child protection, consumer protection, competition law,**» Microsoft vice president and president **Brad Smith** said in Davos. But others say there should be a standard set of rules to specifically regulate AI technologies.

concerned about the tasks that lie ahead of us – fighting the climate crisis, improving people’s health and well-being, ensuring our children’s

education, and training people in the workforce – we can do them without the power of AI,» Prabhakar said. «In the American approach, we have always thought of *this regulatory work as a means of protecting not only national security but also as a means of protecting the rights that are necessary to achieve these great aspirations.*» [10] If we think that we can solve the global problems that we face today, such as climate change, health, peace, and so on, by relying on AI, we are mistaken. It can be partially solved, but if AI gets out of control, these problems will be nothing, because the fate of humanity is at stake.

These controversies always cause discussion in international forums, as one group of scientists says that artificial intelligence should be regulated, while others are against this idea.

«The 2024 Annual Meeting of the World Economic Forum in Davos, Switzerland, was held in late January under the theme of «restoring trust’, with artificial intelligence (AI) emerging as a central theme, sparking critical debates about its potential, challenges and responsible development. » [11] Leaders across industries and sectors grappled with the transformative power of AI, recognizing the need for ethical frameworks and responsible governance to ensure its benefits reach all.

«The theme of recognizing AI as a double-edged sword, both in terms of its potential and its risks, was raised. The potential of AI to revolutionize a variety of fields, from healthcare and scientific discovery to education and business, was widely acknowledged. At the same time, concerns about job displacement, algorithmic bias, and the misuse of AI for malicious purposes were also actively discussed [12].»

emphasizes its benefits to humanity, such as advances in medicine, and its harm to humanity. This description fits AI very well.

«OpenAI CEO Sam Altman stressed the need for an «AI safety plan,» calling for careful and proactive measures to mitigate potential risks. The forum witnessed a strong call for international cooperation to develop ethical guidelines and rules for the development and deployment of artificial intelligence. This includes ensuring transparency and accountability in AI systems, as well as reducing the risk of bias and discrimination [13].

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United Nations Secretary-General Antonio Guterres has advocated a human-centered approach to the development of artificial intelligence, emphasizing the importance of «putting people at the center of AI.»

In conclusion, artificial intelligence has now deviated from its original purpose. Currently, some countries have introduced the use of robot nurses, self-driving cars, and drones for various services. Scientists are trying to make them

as human- like as possible. As you can see, the role of artificial intelligence in our lives is increasing day by day. The fact that artificial intelligence has become a problem is also worrying scientists. It is your and our task to convey to people the dangers it is expected to cause and to prepare them spiritually in some sense. Artificial intelligence may be smarter than humans, but it can never love or be kind, so let's not become like robots. After all, the law of nature should not be violated.

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